

Saliva Based Oral Cancer Screening System using GFP Expressing Yeast Cells

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Supplementary Figures

Figure 1: Lane 1: Restriction digestion product of the two plasmids inserted isolated from transformed yeast cell. **Lane 2:** The size of the upper first band is at 8827bp and the second band is at 6396bp position in lane gene ladder. **Lane 3:** Negative control

Figure 2 (a): The size of the band is at 1800bp in Lane 1 whereas the gene ladder was run in lane M. The insert size has confirmed the presence of TGF β RII transformation in yeast cells.

Figure 2 (b): The size of the band is at 407bp in lane M whereas the gene ladder was run in lane 1. The insert size has confirmed the presence of Col2a1 transformation in yeast cells.

Figure 3: 12.5% SDS PAGE of TGF β RII protein. **Lane 1:** pre-stained protein ladder, **Lane 2:** un-transformed yeast cells (15 μ L), **Lane 3:** TGF β RII in co-transformed yeast cells at 24hr, **Lane 4:** TGF β RII in co-transformed yeast cells at 48hr (15 μ L), **Lane 5:** TGF β RII in co-transformed yeast cells at 72hr, **Lane 6:** TGF β RII in co-transformed yeast cells at 96hr (15 μ L), **Lane 7:** TGF β RII in co-transformed yeast cells at 120 hr. **Lane 8:** TGF β RII in co-transformed yeast cells at 120 hr (15 μ L). **Lane 9:** TGF β RII in co-transformed yeast cells at 120 hr. **Lane 10:** TGF β RII in co-transformed yeast cells at 120 hr.

Figure 4: Col2GF expression plasmids were observed in oral cancer patients' saliva. **(a)** Untreated expression of yeast cells without subjected to patients' saliva. **(b)** Reaction of patient's saliva with TGF β -receptor II plasmid. **(c)** Reaction of patient's saliva with Col2a1 plasmid. **(d)** Highest expression of fluorescence seen in oral cancer patients' saliva treated with co-transformed plasmids. The images were acquired with a fluorescence microscope equipped with a 40 \times objective lens. Scale bar: 20 μ m. The exposure time was 1/15s.

Figure 5: The Bar Graph Indicates Saliva Cancer Markers Expression in Normal and Oral Cancer Patients. (a) Shows Enhanced Expression of TGF β in Saliva. (b) Shows Increased Expression of VEGF in Saliva. (c) Shows Decreased Level of P53 in Saliva. (d) Shows Upregulation of Saliva in TNF- α . (e) Shows Enhanced Expression Of IL-6 in Saliva. (f) Shows Upregulation Of IL-1 in Saliva. A bar graph is drawn to display the frequency distribution graphically. The height of the bar shows the relative distribution of each category of cancer markers. T-test was applied and values were expressed as \pm SEM. ($p < 0.05$ was consider as significant). (* shows the significant difference between normal and cancer patients).

Figure 6: The bar graph indicates TGF- β Lysate expressions according to plasmids after reaction with saliva of oral cancer patients. A bar graph is drawn to display the frequency distribution graphically. The height of the bar shows relative distribution of each category of

TGF- β yeast lysate expression. The Blue bar shows that the Yeast cells with co-transformation 2 plasmids are higher in number as compare to un-cloned Yeast cells, cloned with TGF- β plasmid and Yeast cells cloned with Col2a1 plasmid individually.

Figure 7: The Bar Graph Indicates Serum Cancer Markers Expression in Normal and Oral Cancer Patients. **(a)** Shows increased Expression of TGF β in Serum. **(b)** Shows enhanced Expression of VEGF in Serum. **(c)** Shows Decreased Level of P53 in Serum. **(d)** Shows enhanced expression of Serum in TNF- α . **(e)** Shows Upregulation of IL-6 in Serum. **(f)** Shows increased expression of IL-1 in Serum. A bar graph is drawn to display the frequency distribution graphically. The height of the bar shows the relative distribution of each category of cancer markers. T-test was applied and values were expressed as \pm SEM. ($p < 0.05$ consider as significant). (* shows the significant difference between normal and cancer patients).

Supplementary Figure 8: MAPK cascades of *S. Cerevisiae* in vegetatively growing yeast. Yeast has five MAPK pathways: pheromone response activates Fus3p, Filamentation/invasion activates Kss1p, high osmolarity growth activates Hog1p, cell integrity activates Slit2p and spores wall assembly activates Smk1p (Gustin *et al.*, 1998).

Supplementary Figure 9: Interleukin-6 role in JAK/STAT3 signaling pathway (Yuqi Guo *et al.*, 2012).

Supplementary Figure 10: All three isoforms of tumor growth factor beta (TGF- β) (Roberts & Sporn, 1993).

Figure 11 a

Figure 11 b

Supplementary Figure 11 a & 11 b: pGF1 map for cloning of Col2a1, (a) restriction enzymes sites are SpeI and BamHI, Col2a1 promoter along with four repeated enhancer region are shown and additional NheI restriction enzyme site is introduced **(b)** the size of the transformed plasmid vector is 8827

Supplementary Figure 12: pCMV5B map for cloning of TGF- β receptor II wt, the restriction enzyme sites are BamH1 and KpnI, and total plasmid size is 6396

Homo sapiens transforming growth factor beta receptor 2 (TGFB2), transcript

Sequence ID: [NM_003242.6](#) Length: 4530 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 255 to 1986 [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#)

[Next Match](#) [Prev Match](#)

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
3199 bits(1732)	0.0	1732/1732(100%)	0/1732(0%)	Plus/Plus
Query 122	TCGGTCTATGACGAGCAGCGGGGTCTGCCATGGGTCGGGGGCTGCTCAGGGGCCTGTGGC	181		
Sbjct 255	TCGGTCTATGACGAGCAGCGGGGTCTGCCATGGGTCGGGGGCTGCTCAGGGGCCTGTGGC	314		
Query 182	CGCTGCACATCGTCCTGTGGACGCGTATCGCCAGCACGATCCCACCGCACGTTTCAGAAAT	241		
Sbjct 315	CGCTGCACATCGTCCTGTGGACGCGTATCGCCAGCACGATCCCACCGCACGTTTCAGAAAT	374		
Query 242	CGGTTAATAACGACATGATAGTCACTGACAACAACGGTGCAGTCAAGTTTCCACAACCTGT	301		
Sbjct 375	CGGTTAATAACGACATGATAGTCACTGACAACAACGGTGCAGTCAAGTTTCCACAACCTGT	434		
Query 302	GTAAATTTTGTGATGTGAGATTTTCCACCTGTGACAACCAGAAATCCTGCATGAGCAACT	361		
Sbjct 435	GTAAATTTTGTGATGTGAGATTTTCCACCTGTGACAACCAGAAATCCTGCATGAGCAACT	494		
Query 362	GCAGCATCACCTCCATCTGTGAGAAGCCACAGGAAGTCTGTGTGGCTGTATGGAGAAAAGA	421		
Sbjct 495	GCAGCATCACCTCCATCTGTGAGAAGCCACAGGAAGTCTGTGTGGCTGTATGGAGAAAAGA	554		
Query 422	ATGACGAGAACATAAACAACACTAGAGACAGTTTGCCATGACCCCAAGCTCCCCTACCATGACT	481		
Sbjct 555	ATGACGAGAACATAAACAACACTAGAGACAGTTTGCCATGACCCCAAGCTCCCCTACCATGACT	614		
Query 482	TTATTCTGGAAGATGCTGCTTCTCCAAAGTGCATTATGAAGGAAAAAAAAAGCCTGGTG	541		
Sbjct 615	TTATTCTGGAAGATGCTGCTTCTCCAAAGTGCATTATGAAGGAAAAAAAAAGCCTGGTG	674		
Query 542	AGACTTTCTTCATGTGTTCTGTAGCTCTGATGAGTGCAATGACAACATCATCTTCTCAG	601		
Sbjct 675	AGACTTTCTTCATGTGTTCTGTAGCTCTGATGAGTGCAATGACAACATCATCTTCTCAG	734		


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Query 1322 TAACCTGCTGCCTGTGTGACTTTGGGCTTTCCCTGCGTCTGGACCCTACTCTGTCTGTGG 1381
Sbjct 1455 TAACCTGCTGCCTGTGTGACTTTGGGCTTTCCCTGCGTCTGGACCCTACTCTGTCTGTGG 1514
Query 1382 ATGACCTGGCTAACAGTGGGCAGGTGGGAACTGCAAGATACATGGCTCCAGAAGTCCTAG 1441
Sbjct 1515 ATGACCTGGCTAACAGTGGGCAGGTGGGAACTGCAAGATACATGGCTCCAGAAGTCCTAG 1574
Query 1442 AATCCAGGATGAATTTGGAGAATGTTGAGTCCTTCAAGCAGACCGATGTCTACTCCATGG 1501
Sbjct 1575 AATCCAGGATGAATTTGGAGAATGTTGAGTCCTTCAAGCAGACCGATGTCTACTCCATGG 1634
Query 1502 CTCTGGTGCTCTGGGAAATGACATCTCGCTGTAATGCAGTGGGAGAAGTAAAAGATTATG 1561
Sbjct 1635 CTCTGGTGCTCTGGGAAATGACATCTCGCTGTAATGCAGTGGGAGAAGTAAAAGATTATG 1694
Query 1562 AGCCTCCATTTGGTTCCAAGGTGCGGGAGCACCCCTGTGTGCGAAAGCATGAAGGACAACG 1621
Sbjct 1695 AGCCTCCATTTGGTTCCAAGGTGCGGGAGCACCCCTGTGTGCGAAAGCATGAAGGACAACG 1754
Query 1622 TGTTGAGAGATCGAGGGCGACCAGAAATTTCCAGCTTCTGGCTCAACCACCAGGGCATCC 1681
Sbjct 1755 TGTTGAGAGATCGAGGGCGACCAGAAATTTCCAGCTTCTGGCTCAACCACCAGGGCATCC 1814
Query 1682 AGATGGTGTGTGAGACGTTGACTGAGTGCTGGGACCACGACCCAGAGGCCCGTCTCACAG 1741
Sbjct 1815 AGATGGTGTGTGAGACGTTGACTGAGTGCTGGGACCACGACCCAGAGGCCCGTCTCACAG 1874
Query 1742 CCCAGTGTGTGGCAGAACGCTTCAGTGAGCTGGAGCATCTGGACAGGCTCTCGGGGAGGA 1801
Sbjct 1875 CCCAGTGTGTGGCAGAACGCTTCAGTGAGCTGGAGCATCTGGACAGGCTCTCGGGGAGGA 1934
Query 1802 GCTGCTCGGAGGAGAAGATTCTGAAGACGGCTCCCTAAACACTACCAAATA 1853
Sbjct 1935 GCTGCTCGGAGGAGAAGATTCTGAAGACGGCTCCCTAAACACTACCAAATA 1986

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Supplementary Figure 13: TGF beta receptor II is about 1800bp gene present in pCMV5B backbone. The construct is digested with KpnI at 5' and BamH at 3'. The target gene is confirmed with given primer located 576 position (Forward primer) and at 2681 position (reverse primer) in reverse primer. The given sequence b/w this primer is about 2015bp which is our target sequence present in construct. The sequence was blast to confirmed our gene which shows 100 percent identity as shown in diagram.

Supplementary Figure 14: Transformed pTGF1-4eCol2a1 E. Coli growth on agar plate, 1.5% agar with LB broth, with 50 μ l/ml ampicillin. A good growth of the colonies (OD_{600}) was observed and colonies were picked and further incubated overnight. Then the 700ul of E. coli mixed with 300ul of 30% glycerol solution.

Supplementary Figure 15: Transformed TGF- β E. Coli agar plate, 1.5% agar with LB broth, with 50 μ l/ml ampicillin. The growth of the colonies (OD_{600}) was observed on petri plate and colonies were picked for further growth by incubated overnight. Then the 700ul of E. coli mixed with 300ul of 30% glycerol solution.

Supplementary Figure 16: pCMV5B-TGF- β receptor II plasmid had shown high concentration than pTGF1-4eCol2a1 plasmid

Supplementary Figure 17: pCMV5B-TGF- β receptor II wt vector construct, the pCMV5B-TGF- β receptor II (6396 bp) plasmid is shown a fine band on the agarose gel in lane 1, which marked the confirmation of respective plasmids. This isolated plasmid was saved in vials for the yeast transformation.

Supplementary Figure 18: pGF1-4ecol2a1 plasmid band has shown on gel electrophoresis, the pGF1Col2a1 plasmid (8827 bp) is shown a fine band on the agarose gel in lane 3 as 2 negative controls were run in lane 1 and 2 which marked the confirmation of respective plasmids. This isolated plasmid was saved in vials for the yeast transformation.

Supplementary Figure 19: The growth of yeast cells, the petri plate is showing good growth of transformed yeast cells under optimum condition. The ampicillin selection media helps to grow only transformed cells as ampicillin resistance gene is present on plasmid.

Supplementary Figure 20: Hybrid vector construct containing transformed colonies growth on YAPD plates, the petri plate is showing good growth of hybrid construct containing transformed yeast cells under optimum condition. The ampicillin selection media helps to grow only transformed cells as ampicillin resistance gene is present on plasmid.

Supplementary Figure 21: The TGFβR2 plasmid containing yeast cells are transformed with COL2A1 plasmid and results are confirmed by the growth of the colonies on ampicillin media. The minipreparation is performed for the plasmid isolation and represented on agarose gel. The plasmid isolation by miniprep has shown the confirmation of TGFβR2 plasmid into yeast cells. The circular plasmid is shown in lane 1 whereas the gene ladder is run in lane M.

Supplementary Figure 22: The thick gel band in lane 1 against gene ladder in lane M, is showing the transformation of both plasmids which is further confirmed by Enzyme digestion.

Supplementary Figure 23: The size of the upper first band is at 8827bp and the second band is at 6396bp position in lane M against the gene ladder in lane 1 whereas negative control was run in lane 2 and 3, which is indicating the COL2A1 plasmid and TGF β R2 plasmid, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 24: The size of the band is at 1800bp in lane 1 whereas the gene ladder was run in lane M. The insert size has confirmed the presence of TGF- β receptor II transformation in yeast cells.

Supplementary Figure 25: The size of the band is at 407bp in lane M whereas the gene ladder was run in lane 1. The insert size has confirmed the presence of COL2A1 transformation in yeast cells.

Supplementary Figure 26: 12.5% SDS PAGE of TGF-b r2 protein. L1: pre-stained protein ladder, L2: 15 μ L loaded sample of un-transformed yeast cells, L3: 15 μ L sample of TGF-b r2 in co-transformed yeast cells at 24hr, L4: 15 μ L sample of TGF-b r2 in co-transformed yeast cells at 48hr, L5: 15 μ L sample of TGF-b r2 in co-transformed yeast cells at 72hr, L6: 15 μ L sample of TGF-b r2 in co-transformed yeast cells at 96hr, L7: expression of 15 μ L sample of TGF-b r2 in co-transformed yeast cells at 120 hr. L8: expression of 15 μ L sample of TGF-b r2 in co-transformed yeast cells at 120 hr. L9: expression of 15 μ L sample of TGF-b r2 in co-transformed yeast cells at 120 hr. L10: expression of 15 μ L sample of TGF-b r2 in co-transformed yeast cells at 120 hr.

Supplementary Tables

All tables and graphs are included in excel sheet.

Table no.	Description
Supplementary Table S1	Level of growth factors and cytokines in saliva of normal and oral cancer patients
Supplementary Table S2	Level of growth factors and cytokines in serum of normal and oral cancer patients
Supplementary Table S3	ELISA values for TGF β RII activity
Supplementary Table S4	List of abbreviations
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Supplementary Table S6	Recipe of LB Agar
Supplementary Table S7	Recipe of Glycerol Stock (30%)
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Supplementary Table S12	Primers sequences of Housekeeping genes
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